

FEATURES OF INCREASING THE LEVEL OF EMPLOYMENT IN OUR COUNTRY

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Abstract

In this article, during the years of independence, the issues of raising the standard of living of the population, providing decent jobs and personnel training, special attention paid to young people in the labor market, ways and problems of ensuring employment of the population in our republic, an objective assessment of the situation in the labor market, proposals and recommendations on determining the number of working-age population in accordance with international standards and forming the procedure for developing the balance of labor resources and increasing the employment level of the population in our country.

Key words

Labor market, intellectual potential, jobs, population employment, state employment departments, collective agreement system, labor force, free economic and small industrial zones, working population, labor resources.

In the years of independence, great attention was paid to the issues of raising the standard of living of the population, providing decent jobs, and training personnel. At the same time, significant progress is being made as a result of effective economic reforms and a number of positive changes in areas related to intellectual potential.

Due to the special attention paid to young people in the labor market, the share of employment in relation to the total population is high. Systematic work was launched to help them find a worthy place in society and to support them to work by showing initiative. Young people who use the created opportunities effectively show their abilities in all fields. Consequently, the task of meeting the need for independent and innovative thinking young personnel, who deeply feel responsibility for the country's fate, is becoming increasingly important.

State employment departments play an important role in solving the problems of ensuring employment of the population in our republic. In the system of socio-

economic relations that arise in the labor market, the relationship between employers and hired employees in determining the employment and working conditions of the population, solving one or another social problem, and eliminating social and labor conflicts has a central place. occupies In the labor market, these relations are regulated on the basis of collective, personal and regional methods. Collective agreements are based on the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Convention and recommendations of the International Labor Organization (ILO). As stated in the ILO Convention (paragraph 54), "Collective negotiations, on the one hand, between an entrepreneur and a group of entrepreneurs, and on the other hand, between one or more organizations of workers:

- a) determination of working conditions and employment;
- b) regulation of relations between entrepreneurs and workers;
- c) refers to all negotiations conducted for the purposes of regulating relations between entrepreneurs or their organizations and the organization or organizations of workers.

The most important advantage of the application of such regulation in the labor market is that the decisions made in it are extremely flexible (flexible, flexible), they cannot be compared to legislative, judicial or administrative methods. The regulation of labor relations is the strictness of the complex contract system, as well as having widespread correct ideas about the realization of the principles of equality and social justice in the field of relations. An individual employee cannot show resistance to the employer, who is much stronger than him in negotiations, by his actions alone. Moreover, according to the collective agreement, the workplace of the workforce with low qualifications and insufficiently high productivity is kept for a certain period of time. The collective agreement is important in achieving the stability of labor relations. The system of collective agreement cannot eliminate conflicts in the relations of economic entities in the labor market by itself. Because these conflicts are based on differences in social interests, goals, aspirations, and demands. Although the system of collective agreements provides for the process of agreeing interests, reaching a mutual decision and quickly resolving conflicts, the negotiation process also creates the possibility of achieving more favorable results. At the moment, the terms of the agreement take the form of a contract, forcing both parties to act in order to ensure social and economic stability on the basis of these conditions, without taking the last measures, that is, without allowing strikes or layoffs.

The increase in the demand for labor force and its supply are more effective methods of regulating the market for the regions of the republic with excess labor resources, first of all, Andijan, Fergana, Namangan, Tashkent, Samarkand, Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya, Bukhara and Khorezm regions. it is necessary to calculate the decrease.

Methods of regulation of labor resources in the market

Today, 23 free economic zones and 348 small industrial zones are operating in our country. 453 projects with a total value of 2.6 billion dollars have been implemented in free economic zones and about 36 thousand jobs have been created. In small industrial zones, 1497 projects worth 5 trillion soums have been launched and employment of more than 36000 people has been provided. Industrial zones are a very convenient place for the activities of our entrepreneurs, they are gaining importance in providing employment to the population and implementing many large projects. Nevertheless, there are many untapped opportunities in these zones. It is no exaggeration to say that the decision of the head of our state "On measures to further develop the engineering and communication infrastructure of special economic and small industrial zones" was a historical document aimed at expanding these opportunities. This document was the solution to the problems of entrepreneurs in economic zones in terms of infrastructure. According to the decision, 1.6 trillion soums allocated for the improvement of infrastructure in economic zones will make it easier for entrepreneurs to place newly developed projects. This is a great opportunity not only for local businessmen, but also for foreign investors and our citizens.

The head of our state emphasized that the most important issue is the timely launch of projects in free economic and small industrial zones. This year, it is planned to launch 332 projects with a total value of 1.1 billion dollars in free

economic zones, and 1845 projects with a total value of 9.5 trillion soums in small industrial zones.

Today, everyone recognizes that the most appropriate way to provide the population with profitable work is to introduce the "neighborhood" work system in the regions. In particular, this system is important in supporting the entrepreneurial initiatives of the population, especially young people and women. In the Republic of Karakalpakstan, 418 employees of commercial banks were assigned as permanent representatives to the neighborhoods to study the sources of income of families, their needs for useful work "household-wise" and the problems of entrepreneurs "customer-wise" and quickly solve them.

It is advisable to use the data of the State Statistics Committee and the results of the study of employment issues of the Ministry of Labor in order to objectively assess the situation in the labor market, determine the number of working-age population in accordance with international standards, and formulate the procedure for developing the balance of labor resources. According to the data of the balance of labor resources, the total labor resources of the republic in 2022 will be 18.3 million people, of which 99.4 percent will be working-age population, and the rest will be working teenagers and pensioners.

In addition, it should be noted that 75.3 percent of labor resources or 13.8 million people belong to the category of economically active population, of which 13.1 million people belong to the category of employed population. It can be seen that the employment rate of the economically active population is 94.8 percent. The remaining 4.5 million people in the structure of labor resources are economically inactive population, which make up 24.7 percent of the total labor resources. As we mentioned above, by the end of 2022, the employment rate of the population was 94.8 percent in relation to the economically active population, and 71.4 percent in relation to labor resources.

Thanks to the effective functioning of the conditions and support mechanisms created for the development of small business in the country, the population's business ability is expanding, and the entrepreneurial initiative of young people is increasing. These aspects, in turn, pave the way for timely promotion of promising proposals and initiatives. As a result, the majority of the employed population works in the small business sector, and the sector's share in the GDP is increasing. The fact that a wide path has been opened for the development of KBXT has become an important factor in the increase of employment and income of the population, and it has become one of the means of ensuring the stability of the society and the consistent development of the economy.

This creates a solid foundation for ensuring macroeconomic stability, economic development, and consistent growth of the population's standard of living and quality. Increasing incomes, in turn, qualitatively changes the financial situation of families. This is the most important, so to speak, priority. In this case, modernization of industrial enterprises, providing them with modern technologies makes it possible to produce competitive products for the world market.

The mentioned considerations show that it is necessary to increase the level of employment of the economically active population in our country. For this purpose, by further improving the "Methodology for calculating the unemployed population in need of employment by region", developing the "Methodology for the development of the report and perspective balance of labor resources, employment and employment of the population" and in the regions of the republic it is necessary to introduce its use in practice.

Report and forecast balances of labor resources, employment and population employment are developed for the following purposes:

The following should be reflected in this methodology:

First, the model structure of the labor resources, employment and employment balance of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In order to eliminate possible difficulties in determining the future, this sample structure should reflect the name of the indicators, their calculation

algorithm, the balance of the report, the estimate (for the current year) and the balance of the forecast (for the next year).

Also, in the lines of the model structure: the number of labor resources, that is, the number of economically active and economically inactive population by types; labor supply and demand and the difference between them (balance "+" or "-") by types; there should be a level of employment of the population in the cross-section of categories.

Second, the scheme of providing information for the formation of the balance of labor resources, employment and employment of the population.

In this scheme, it is advisable to clearly indicate the content (name) of the information, the name of the ministry and office providing the information, the period of providing the information, and where it is being provided.

Third, the organizational scheme for developing the balance of labor resources, employment and employment of the population.

The scheme should include the name of the measures, implementation stages and deadlines, as well as organizations responsible for implementation, and should be in the following four areas:

- formation of information base;
- development of the balance sheet;
- development of forecast balance;
- their application in practice.

After the model structures and schemes mentioned above have been developed and approved, the official ministries and agencies of the republic should develop a report balance of labor resources, employment and employment of the population in the Republic of Uzbekistan based on these structures and schemes.

Also, in addition to the balance sheet, it is necessary to develop a forecast balance sheet for the next year of labor resources, employment and employment of the population by the official ministries and departments:

- population forecast indicators (demographic forecast);
- reporting balance of labor resources, employment and population employment;
- forecast parameters of development of socio-economic and economic network of the republic and regions;
- forecast indicators of graduates of educational institutions entering the labor market;
- information on the assessment of personnel needs in the networks of state and economic management bodies is used.

It can be said that by developing the above-mentioned methodology and putting it into practice, comprehensive, qualitative and objective analysis of labor resources, employment and employment of the population, young people entering the labor market for the first time, increasing the level of employment ground is created for This allows to use in the development of projects of the program of creation of jobs and employment of the population every year, and to increase its efficiency in practice.

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